

MINIPACK: CULTURE AND SOCIETY

GAMES AND ACTIVITIES FOR INTERCULTURAL LEARNING THROUGH PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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MINIPACK: CULTURE AND SOCIETY

BUILDING INTERCULTURAL AND SOCIAL COMPETENCIES THROUGH PHYSICAL EDUCATION

STEP: DESIGN AND PLAN

EXAMPLES OF ACTIVITIES FOR INTERCULTURAL LEARNING THROUGH PHYSICAL EDUCATION

Each school has a unique intercultural environment and context. Moreover, every class, especially those with multicultural backgrounds, is specific and distinct. Therefore, it is essential to understand the characteristics of your students, your school, and your local community in order to design activities that fit within this context. To support this process, we have developed a set of activities and games that can easily adapt to various intercultural settings and different segments of physical education (PE) classes.

These activities are designed to foster different dimensions of intercultural learning, including intercultural awareness, communication, and sensitivity. Each set of activities aims to address specific educational challenges that may arise in multicultural settings, both in primary and secondary schools. The suggested activities can be effortlessly integrated into various themes within different PE curricula and can be implemented in numerous ways. They can be used throughout the school year as part of regular PE classes, incorporated into individual lessons, included as active breaks during recess, or offered as part of extracurricular activities.

The table below provides an overview of various activities and games aimed at promoting different aspects of intercultural learning. For each activity, you will find a description, a list of required materials and equipment, reflective prompts for students, possible modifications to the activity, and specific tips for teachers to facilitate implementation.

Table 1: Overview of activities and games for developing different aspects of intercultural learning

Dimension	Activities for primary school students	Activities for secondary school students
Intercultural awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Movement game: “It is ME” • Traditional dance • Intercultural puzzle • International music chair 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Movement game: “It is ME and my intercultural ME” • Traditional dance activity • Traditional game activity
Intercultural communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Find your country fellow • Come, stop, wait game • Scarf toss game • Mirror game • Blindfold stroll game • Number race • Opposite movement game 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quickly through the loop • Group twister atomic game • Get together • Many greetings • Sights from all over the world • Games from around the world
Intercultural sensitivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • My cultural hat • Greeting games • Traditional cloths • Traditional game “Colin Maillard (Engl. Blindman’s Buff)” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Find your culture, find your home” • Traditional sports

1.0 EXAMPLES OF ACTIVITIES FOR INTERCULTURAL AWARENESS

Intercultural awareness refers to knowledge of multiple elements of own culture as well as knowledge and understanding of elements of other cultures. Knowledge and understanding of own culture provide a deeper understanding of personal identity and self-awareness, while knowledge and understanding of other cultures develop awareness of the existence of other cultures and acceptance of other cultures. Intercultural awareness provides an understanding of both own and other cultures, particularly similarities and differences between them. Awareness of similarities and differences between cultures makes one more likely to understand and accept them. These similarities and differences can refer to surface elements such as food, language, music, games, and dances; and deeper aspects such as attitude, beliefs, values, communication styles etc. The final step is the understanding and acceptance of similarities and differences in the context of culture.

Educational problem: Schools are places where children from different cultural, ethnic, and religious backgrounds are engaged. Such differences can often cause misunderstanding and conflicts that can be transferred from the classroom, at the school level or out in the community. On the other hand, schools can be also places that can support understanding differences, celebrate the uniqueness and specifics of different cultures, and provide understanding and support. Working on students' cultural identity, self-awareness of their own culture, and becoming aware of other cultures is important for educating students who are citizens of the world united in differences.

Aim: The presented activities aim to develop students' awareness of their own culture and cultural identity, and awareness of other cultures; and to identify, understand, and accept similarities and differences between cultures through cooperative games, traditional dances, and traditional movement games.

Learning Outcomes

Students will be able to:

- Understand and recognize differences and similarities in beliefs, attitudes, and personal preferences between classmates, based on different cultural identities.
- Learn about the existence of different types of dances, music, and games in different cultures. Acquire knowledge and understanding of other cultures;
- Gain the ability to perceive others accurately; develop an open mindset and flexibility when communicating and cooperating with classmates and people with different cultural backgrounds.
- Explore and gain experience and knowledge of different cultures and their specifics by practicing different national dances and traditional games.

Implementation

Students will discover specifics for their classmates and different cultures through their involvement in games; practice different traditional dances and at this way identify similarities and differences between cultures; and understand culture specifics through personal involvement, interaction, and cooperation with people from different cultures. The students will have an active role in learning while the role of teachers will be mainly supportive. Student-centered teaching approach will be adopted, and the strategies of collaboration and discovery will be applied, where students will have active participation, and each student will have the opportunity to learn different things and be involved in different types of activities.

Facility of implementation: Schoolyard, court, classroom.

1.1. INTERCULTURAL AWARENESS FOR PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

Movement game: “It is ME”	Activity description			
	<p>All the children are lined up creating a circle or in one row with no order of standing. In front of them, in the middle of the schoolyard or in the middle of the court, there is a smaller circle marked with a longer rope. The teacher reads different statements related to different personal characteristics and later cultural specific characteristics. If children recognize themselves in some of the statements, they should jump into the circle, shake hands with some of the children who are also in the circle, and get back by running backward to their place.</p> <p>The first phase of the game: the statements are more in general and common for all children. For example: “I have blue eyes”, “I love pop music”, “I like the green color”, “I like to dance” etc.</p> <p>The second phase of the game: the statements are more culturally related, connected with specifics of some cultures. We can ask children to recognize themselves based on their culture or tradition (in classes where there are children with different cultural backgrounds) or play the game based on what they like and can belong to their culture or other cultures. For example: “In our home, we eat with chopsticks”, “Some of my relatives wear traditional clothes”, “I like Brazilian dance”, “In my culture, we handshake when we meet” etc.</p>			
	Materials:	Reflection	Modification	Tips for teachers
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a long rope, • a list of prepared statements for the teachers 	<p>After 15 minutes of playing the game, children get together and discuss what they learned about themselves and their classmates; their feelings etc.</p> <p>Reflective questions: Teachers can use some of the following questions: Who you were most similar to? In what you were different from your classmates? How does make you feel similar? How does make you feel different than most of the children? Did you learn something new from your classmates? Answers to these questions should lead to a discussion about similarities and differences between us, the different cultures that we belong to etc. This discussion can be used as an introduction for further learning on other classes or as a conclusion that we can be different in one</p>	<p>Modifications and adjustments can be done for different age groups in terms of applied movement activities and used statements during the game.</p> <p>In terms of movements, children can be given instructions to jump in different ways (jump with one leg, jump with both legs, run forward, run backward, crawl, run into the circle, and leave a sticker etc). Variations can be made with the distance of the place where children stand and the marked circle. In terms of statements, teachers can choose different questions depending on what aspect of intercultural awareness they want to work on.</p> <p>The game can also be modified and applied in the classroom setting with less demanding</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Choose tasks based on the age and the skills of your students. • When choosing statements, be aware of the cultural background of the children in your class and try to include some statements that will refer to their specifics • Use statements that are short, clear, and easy to understand. • Encourage children to be free to express themselves and to be honest.

		thing and similar in another and that makes the beauty of being together.	movements or using movements that require little space.	
Traditional dances games	Activity			
	<p>Before the actual activity happens, the teacher should search for some simple traditional dances from different cultures. Depending on the structure of the class, the teacher can choose traditional dances from cultures that children in the class belong to or can be traditional dance from other completely different countries. Depending on the age of the children, during one class, two or three dances can be done.</p> <p>Activity description: The activity starts with playing music and a demonstration of one of the selected dances. The teacher or some of the children can do the presentation. The next step is to teach all the other children to dance together. After several attempts, the second selected dance should be presented, and children should learn to dance it.</p>			
	Materials	Reflection	Modification	Tips for teachers
CD player, music for different traditional dances Duration: 20 minutes.	After practicing both dances, the teacher initiates a discussion about how similar or different the dances and music were; can children guess the country of origin of the dance and the music; how they felt while dancing; danced similar to their traditional ones, etc. This discussion can be followed with additional tasks for children in terms of finding out more about the dance, clothing, country of origin, other specifics of the country etc.	Different modifications can be made, depending on the structure of the class (cultural background of the children), age of the children, educational goals etc. Based on this, the teacher can choose national traditional dance, traditional dances that represent the culture of every child in the class, or traditional dances from completely different countries aimed to be familiar with other traditions and cultures. With older children, the teacher gives a task to each child to discuss with their parents and together to choose and learn some simple traditional dance, specific to their culture. They should also choose music for it and if possible, provide a link with the dance to the teacher. During the activity, each child should present their selected dance and invite other classmates to dance it all together.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Choose dances based on the age and the skills of your students. They should be easy to understand and repeat. Be aware of the cultural background of the children in your class and try to include dances of all cultures that children in your class belong to. Prepare appropriate music and good sound when performing the dances. Encourage children to be free to express themselves and try every dance regardless of their skills Try to make a friendly and relaxed atmosphere. When possible, connect the dance with other specifics of the culture. Try to establish integration and 	

				correlation links with other subjects.
Intercultural puzzle Duration: 20 minutes.	Activity			
	<p>The teacher should prepare 2, 3, or 4 different pictures that will represent one country (depending on the number of children in the class and their age). Each picture should refer to a country whose culture should be identified and learned through the game. The picture can have the name of the country and/or the flag and/or both. Connected with each country, there should be a 4 pieces puzzle related to some country-specific relate to its culture (for example food, monument, national clothes, national instrument, sport, dance, well-known tradition, manner of greeting etc).</p> <p>Activity Description: Children are divided into two, three or four equal groups depending on the number of children in the class and their age. Each group is lined up in separate columns. The starting point for each column is marked with tape. 5 small hoops are placed in front of each column. After the markets, one basket is placed. Inside the basket, parts from the puzzle are placed. After the basket, 5 markers in all columns are placed leading to the picture with country name/flag/name & flag.</p> <p>Task for the children: Each child at the beginning of each column should jump with both legs in all hoops placed on the floor. When he/she comes to the basket, takes one part for the puzzle, runs zig-zag around all markers and puts the part from the puzzle under the picture of the country that refers to the element for the puzzle (ex: chopsticks Japan, pasta & spaghetti – Italy etc). Then the child runs back in a straight line towards his/her column, gives a sign by touching the hand of the child that is next in line in its column and goes back at the end of the line. The activity duration is until all puzzle parts are made. The group that finishes first is the winner.</p>			
	Materials	Reflection	Modification	Tips for teachers
	Markers, small hoops, puzzle cards, basket	At the end of the game, the teacher together with all children analyses if the puzzles and matches are correct. If there are wrong solutions, discuss with the children what is the right solution. Children can also reflect on their experiences. Following reflective prompts can be used: How do you feel during this activity? Was it easy or hard? Was it difficult to identify different cultural specifics? Was it easy to cooperate with teammates from your group?	Modifications can be done in the content of the puzzle or in the movement tasks. The number puzzle part can be changed based on children's age. The movement tasks can be also modified based on the level of intensity of movement that we want to achieve as well as the available equipment. Other forms of fundamental movements can be applied. The position of puzzle cards can be also changed, moving it at the starting point or at the end before country pictures. For better results, it will be good if	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The parts of the puzzle and the difficulty of the task should be chosen depending on the age of the children. • Pay attention to the groups to be harmonized in terms of the number of children in each group, and the level of their ability. • Pay attention to how children do the movement tasks.

		Did you learn something new for some country during this game?	specifics of the countries involved in the game are discussed and learned in the classroom during other subjects.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Motivate and encourage children when needed. Encourage their teamwork. • Involve children in the evaluation of the final puzzle. • Don't skip the reflection part and discussion with children
International music chair Duration: 20 minutes.	Activity			
	All children are lined up in a large circle. In the middle of the circle, there are chairs two less than the number of children in the class. All children are invited to stand in the circle. When teachers start some song, children should dance according to the music, using specific dance movements based on the music that is played. When the music stops, each child should sit on one chair in the middle. The one that has no chair leaves the game and one chair is taken out. Before leaving the game, the child that was not able to sit on a free chair should identify the country of origin of the music that was played. The music should be a traditional one, specifically for different countries. It is good if this activity is used after the Traditional dance activity so the children will be already familiar with traditional dances from different countries. The activity finishes when only one child will remain in the game.			
	Materials	Reflection	Modification	Tips for teachers
	CD player, chairs	After finalizing the activity, children should reflect on their experiences. How did they feel doing the activity? Did they find it difficult to identify the origin of the music or the dance? Were they able to identify different music sounds, move on them, and recognize their origin?	The intensity of the activity can be changed by using different tasks – make a larger distance between the place where children dance, and the chairs are places; give a task to go under the chair or stand over the chair when the music stops etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use music that children have used before so they can recognize the dances. • Take care of the safety issues during the game • Encourage children to use different dance moves on different music sounds, and movements that are specific to the music that is played.

1.2. INTERCULTURAL AWARENESS FOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

<p>“It is ME and my intercultural ME”</p> <p>Duration: 20 minutes.</p>	Activity			
	<p>All students are lined up in one line with no order of standing. In front of them, in the middle of the schoolyard or in the middle of the court, there is a long rope. The teacher reads different statements related to different personal characteristics and later cultural specific characteristics. If students recognize themselves in some of the statements, they jump or run to the rope and stand for few seconds, shake hands with some of the classmates that are also there and get back by running backwards to their place.</p> <p>First phase. It's ME: the statements are more in general and common for all students. For example: “I have blue eyes”, “I love pop music”, “I like the green color”, “I like to dance” etc.</p> <p>Second phase. It's my culture: the statements are more culturally related, connected with specifics of some cultures. We can ask students to recognize themselves based on their culture or tradition (in classes where there are children with different cultural backgrounds) or play then game based on what they like and can belong to their culture or other cultures. For example: “In our home, we eat with chopsticks”, “Some of my relatives wear traditional clothes”, “I like Brazilian dance”, “In my culture, we handshake when we meet” etc.</p> <p>Third phase. It's the intercultural ME: We create statements from different cultures and children should recognize what they like in other cultures. Some of the statements can be: “I like Italian pasta”, “I like afro hairstyle”, “I love Brazilian capoeira”, “I enjoy Japanese music” etc.</p>			
	Materials	Reflection	Modification	Tips for teachers
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • long rope • list of prepared statements for the teachers 	<p>After 15 minutes of playing the game, students get together and discuss what they learned about themselves and their classmates; their feelings etc. Reflective questions: Teachers can use some of the following questions: Who you were most similar to? In what you were different from your classmates? How does make you feel similar? How does make you feel different than most of your classmates? Did you learn something new from your classmates? Answers to these questions should lead to a discussion about similarities and differences between us, different cultures that we belong to etc. This discussion can be used as an introduction for further learning on other classes or as a conclusion that we can be different in one thing</p>	<p>Modifications and adjustments can be done for different age groups in terms of applied movement activities and used statements during the game.</p> <p>In terms of movements, students can be instructed to jump on different ways (jump with one leg, jump with both legs, run forward, run backward, crawl; run – touch down and leave a sticker etc). Variations can be made with the distance of the place where students stand.</p> <p>In terms of statements, teachers can choose different questions depending on what aspect of intercultural awareness they want to work on. Also, teachers can invite students to write several statements about their own culture and the</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Choose tasks based on the age and the skills of your students. • When choosing statements, be aware of the cultural background of the children in your class and try to include some statement that will refer to their specifics. • Use statements that are short, clear and easy to understand. • Encourage children to be free to express themselves and to be honest. • 	

		and similar in another and that makes the beauty of being together.	culture they like and then use that during the game.	
<p>Traditional dances games</p> <p>Duration: 20 minutes.</p>	Activity			
	<p>Activity Organization: The teacher gives a task to all students to discuss with their parents/ grandparents and identify and learn some traditional dance. They should also choose a specific traditional music following the dance. The students present the prepared dance to the teacher and based on the number of different dances; the teacher create timeframe for their realization. If several students choose same dance, they will present as a group.</p> <p>Activity Description: The activity starts with playing music and a demonstration of one of the selected dances. The student/students who selected the dance will do the presentation. This can be also supported with video. The next step is to teach all the other students to dance together. After several attempts, all students should dance together. After several attempts, the second selected dance should be presented, and students should learn to dance it too. If there are more different dances, several different classes should be organized.</p>			
	Materials	Reflection	Modification	Tips for teachers
	CD player, music for different traditional dances	After practicing different dances, the teacher initiates discussion how similar or different the dances and music were; can students guess the country of origin of the dance and the music; how they felt while dancing; were dances similar with their traditional once etc. This discussion can be followed with additional tasks for children in terms to find out more about the dance, clothing, country of origin, other specifics of the country etc.	Different modifications can be made, depending on the structure of the class (cultural background of the children), age, educational goals etc. Based on this, the teacher can choose national traditional dance, traditional dances that represent culture of every child in the class, or traditional dances from completely different countries aimed to be familiar with other traditions and cultures.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involve all student and motivate them all to prepare a dance and involve in the activity. • Give clear instructions what should be prepared by children (time, duration, music, how to present) • Prepare required technical support (CD player, speakers etc). • Encourage students to be free to express themselves and try every dance regardless of their skills. Try to make a friendly and relaxed atmosphere. • When possible, connect the dance with other specifics of the culture. Try to establish integration and correlation links with other subjects.

Traditional game activity Duration: 20 minutes	Activity Activity organization and instructions are the same as for traditional dance activities described above. The difference now is that students are asked to select some traditional game specific to their culture, or some game that their parents and grandparents were playing. Or some traditional game from a country that they like. Depending on the number of identified and selected games, the teacher can organize several different activities or in case of the same selected games, create group of students working together.	
	Materials Depending on the selected traditional game	Resources for different games Bronikowska, M., & Laurent, JF. (2015). Recall: Games of the past, Sports for Today. Tafisa http://tafisa.org/traditional-sports-and-games https://www.sportetcityennete.com/en/europe/european-projects/recall-project

2.0. EXAMPLES OF ACTIVITIES FOR INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION

Communication, both verbal and non – verbal is the core element for human relationships. While verbal communication is clearly different in different cultures in terms using different languages, non – verbal communication often can lead to misunderstanding considering that In different cultures, same or similar movements or non – verbal acts can have different meaning. Therefore, understanding cultural similarities and differences in terms of communication styles is very important and needed for avoiding conflicts and misunderstandings. Communication skills and including intercultural communication as well, can be improved using different communication games and cooperative games. These games can improve communication skills and teammates` ability to exchange information. Posture and body movements, facial expressions, tone and nuance of voice, etc. are some of the ways of transmitting and/or understanding the message and determine the effectiveness of communication.

Educational problem: Nonverbal communication is equally important as verbal communication. Even more, many times our body movement, expressions and gestures can even tell more than words. Being aware of different nonverbal gestures and movements that are culturally related is important when working and living in multicultural environment. Not knowing culture specific elements in communication can often lead to misunderstanding and conflict. Therefore, strengthening children knowledge and understanding for intercultural communication can be very important educational lesson.

Aim: The aim of the presented activities is students to understand cultural similarities and differences in nonverbal communication and to develop nonverbal communication skills through cooperative tasks and communication games; to develop students` verbal and nonverbal communication skills through cooperative tasks and communication games.

Learning Outcomes

Students will be able to:

- understand and recognize the different communication styles and cultural codes, the multiple communication skills, and the importance of communication with all despite culture for the achievement of a team goal.
- understand cultural similarities and differences in non – verbal communication
- explore and gain experience with the different ways of communication (body movement, facial expressions), become familiar with the different communication codes and develop skills that contribute to constructive communication. Improve cooperation, teamwork and on task focus on cooperative games regardless of cultural differences.
- to develop communication skills through movement games and activities and gain confidence to interact with people from other culture
- improve their observation, perception, and interpretation skills as important or interpersonal communication by participating in cooperative games and tasks.
- acquire a positive attitude in communicating with other people regardless of culture, build and show self-confidence when communicating, demonstrate effective communication outside of the school environment.

Implementation: Students will explore their codes and communication skills; practice different forms of verbal and nonverbal communication integrated with movement and improve these skills through interaction and cooperation with people from different cultures. The students will have an active role in learning while the teacher's role will be mainly supportive. The student-centered teaching approach will be adopted and the strategies of collaboration, collaborative problem solving, and discovery will be applied. Each student will have the opportunity to participate in different activities that require different types of communication and interaction.

Facility of implementation: Schoolyard, court, classroom.

2.1. INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION FOR PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

Title	Activity description			
FIND YOUR COUNTRY FELLOW	Before starting the activity, the teacher put all cards in a box in the middle of the sport hall or school yard. Explains to children that each of them should take one card and see it without allowing other to see it. Teacher will then give some movement tasks and all children should follow (running forward, running back, jumping on two legs, crawling etc. All children perform the task. When the teacher said "Find your country fellow" children start to perform the movement from their own card and try to identify another child/group of children that are doing the same. This can be repeated several times with changing the movement tasks or switching cards.			
	Materials	Reflection	Modification	Tips for teachers

Duration: 30 minutes.	Materials cards with different country names (or flags) and form of greeting specific for the country should be prepared. There can be 3 or up to 5 different cards depending on the number of children and their age. The total number of cards should be equal to the number of children in the class.	After 15 minutes playing, children get together and discuss their experience and feelings. Was it difficult to perform country specific movement? Did they know it from previously or was a new for them? How did they feel when identify another child doing the same? When did they feel more comfortable – when finding only one child from their culture or joining the whole group? Where there any problems in communication? Was it difficult to identify culture specifics?	The game can be more challenging if by defining place for each country on different parts of the sport hall. After performing different movement tasks given by the teacher, all children with same card should get as fast as they can to the marked place for their country and all perform the specific cultural movement.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Give students clear instructions. • Encourage them to use different movements. • Repeat the activity making different groups.
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Examples of cards for the game FIND YOUR COUNTRY FELLO

India

Japan

Eskimo greeting

France

COME, STOP, WAIT GAME	Activity			
	All children are lined in one line. The teacher stands at the opposite site of the sport hall or school yard. Children are following the signs of the teacher. The teacher can perform different signs for start (rise one hand up), come front (move the hand toward the face), go back or left and right (points the direction with the arm), turn around (making a circle with fingers), wait in place (extend the arm and rise the palm) etc. Also other, not so common nonverbal signs can be agreed and used.			
	Materials	Reflection	Modification	Tips for teachers

Duration: 30 minutes.	Cards with different signs can be used	After finishing the game, children get together and discuss about their experience and feelings. They should reflect on their feelings. Some of the reflective questions can be: How did you feel at the beginning of the game? Was it difficult to memorize all non – verbal signs? Do you use some of those non – verbal signs in your everyday life?	The intensity of the activity and its complexity can be defined by the speed of changing signs by the teacher, number of nonverbal movements included etc. The game can be more challenging and exciting by introducing penalties (the children that misunderstand signs or not follow them properly to do some additional activity (ex: few frog jumps, sit ups etc.). The level of difficulty can be increased by adding some obstacles. Note for teachers: When choosing non – verbal signs, elements from traffic signs used by traffic policemen can be also applied. This will be a good link of non – verbal communication and learning traffic culture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adjust the number of used non – verbal signs to students age and ability; • Adjust the intensity of movements and/or obstacle course according to students' abilities, available space and available equipment. • Give students clear instructions. • Introduce penalties if you want to make the activity more challenging and fun. • Encourage students to support their teams and to play fair.
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SCARF TOSS GAME Duration: 25 minutes.	Activity		
	The class is divided into two equal groups lined up in two opposite rows standing on opposite sites. Each child picks up a partner across. Every child holds a scarf toss. On teachers sign the partners from both groups throw their scarf in the air and run fast front to catch the scarf that was thrown by the partner from opposite side. The point is to throw the scarf up in the air in unpredictable direction and make the movement more difficult. The task requires following body signs and identification of right direction, fast movements, and good coordination.		
	Materials	Reflection	Tips for teachers
scarfs toss for each child	After 15 – 20 minutes of playing the game, children get together and discuss their experience and feelings.	Give students clear instructions and suggestions about the movements that they can use. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allow students to communicate, make decisions, and define their own strategy. • Encourage fair play among teams. • 	
	Activity		
Each child picks a partner. Players partner up and face each other. One player is the leader, and the other the follower. The leader begins to move without speaking, and the follower matches each movement. Movements should be different and can include running in different directions with fast changing direction of movement, jogs, jumps, crawls etc. Participants must rely entirely on body language. After a few minutes, the players switch roles and repeat the exercise.			

MIRROR GAME Duration: 25 minutes.	In terms of intercultural communication, the game can be modified by using different elements from some culture that the leader will present, and the follower should first follow and later identify the presented culture/country of origin etc. Some of presented elements can be movements from some national dance, movements that reflect the sound of the languages, manner of greetings (ex: hand waving and saying Cao Cao in Italy; bowing followed with arm movement specific for Japan and other Asian cultures etc).			
	Reflection	Modification	Tips for teachers	
	After 15 minutes playing, children together and discuss their experience and feelings. They should reflect on their feelings, experiences while being in different positions, some of the reflective questions can be: What was more challenging - to be a leader or follower? What position was more interesting for you? In which position you feel more comfortable? How did you feel in different roles? Where there any problems in communication?	If children are not familiar with different culture elements, the teacher can be the leader and all other children can be the followers. This can be a good introduction game that can be used for intercultural contents within other subjects in the classroom.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Give students clear instructions. • Encourage them to use different movements. • Repeat the activity making different pairs. 	
BLINDFOLD STROLL GAME Duration: 25 minutes.	Activity			
	Set up two identical obstacle courses. It can be different depending on the available equipment and space. Following is an example of one obstacle course: 5 markers lined in straight line, 4 small hoops lined zig – zag; One elastic tape positioned higher (the players should cross under it), one elastic tape positioned lower (the players should cross it above), 4 stickers placed on the floor without order (players should step on each of it), conus marker for returning. Place a box with different crayons next to the conus marker. Return in straight line. At the end of line for each group there is a poster with country flag that is noncolored and different pictures with cultural elements (clothes, food etc). The pictures at one poster should be mixed – half that are correct for the country that flag is presented, and other half should be elements of other cultures			
	Materials	Reflection	Modification	Tips for teachers
different sport equipment for obstacle course (markers, ropes, hoops, elastic tapes, stickers in different colors), eye masks, paper with drawing from flags from different country, crayons (with colors from the flag of different country), pictures with elements	At the end, get the children together and discuss their experience and feelings. They should reflect on their feelings, experiences while being in different positions, problems that they faced with. Some of the reflective questions can be: What was more difficult to be blindfolded or be responsible to lead? How did you feel when you were blindfolded? What were your feelings when	The game can be more challenging, fun and exciting by introducing penalties, involving “spies” in the opposite team that will give wrong	Adjust the obstacle course according to students’ abilities, available space and available equipment. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Give students clear instructions. • Introduce penalties, “spy” or limit time if you want to make the activity more challenging and fun. • Encourage students to support their teams and to play fair. 	

	from different country representing its culture (people in traditional clothes, national food, specific monument, or other cultural symbol etc).	you have the responsibility to lead? Which position was more demanding? Where there any problems in communication? Were they feeling frustrated? Was it difficult to trust the leader partner?	instructions or by limiting time.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allow students to communicate, make decisions how to cooperate in the pair or within the group. • Repeat the activity making different pairs.
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NUMBER RACE ALPHABET RACE Duration 25 minutes	Activity			
	Prepare cards with numbers from 1 to 9. You should prepare as several groups of 1 – 9 cards based on the number of children in the class. Prepare a card with different number combinations (ex: 10936; 105679, 4589321). Make sure that numbers are not repeating. Activity Description: Make 2, 3 or 4 groups depending on the number of children in your class. Each group should be placed in a different corner of the sport hall or courtyard. Mark 2, 3 or 4 lines in the center. On the sign of the teacher (non – verbal) by raising a card with a number, children from each group that have the proper card number should line as fast as they can at the line in the middle creating the number that is on the card shown by the teacher. The group that first lined up creating the required number achieved 5 points, the second group 3 points and the last group 2 points. The task requires both verbal and nonverbal communication between children, cooperation etc.			
	Materials	Reflection	Modification	Tips for teachers
cards with numbers from 1 to 9.	After 15 – 20 minutes of playing the game, children get together and discuss their experience and feelings. Some of the reflective questions can be: How did you feel during the game? Where there any communication problems within your group? How did you help each other? What was the main obstacle for your team?	The game can be played with alphabets instead of numbers. To make it more fun and engaging obstacles can be added on the way to the lines. For older children a difficult task can be added. For example: calculations if played with numbers (567983 -1) or associations if played with letters (ex: opposite of right is...). Another modification can be a lining according to birthday order, where at the beginning of the line will be the children born at the beginning of the month and at the end the one born later. This way requires verbal communication. Another way of modification can be using names in alphabetical order. Children are lining up according to the alphabetical order of their names – one on A starts first, followed by one with names starting on B, C, D... etc.	Give students clear instructions and suggestions about the movements that they can use. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allow students to communicate, make decisions, and define their own strategy. • Encourage fair play among teams. • To make it more challenging, from time to time, give them instructions to use just nonverbal communication. 	

<p>OPPOSITE MOVEMENT GAME</p> <p>Duration 25 minutes</p>	Activity		
	<p>Activity Organization: place bench or chairs or both in different positions in the schoolyard or In the sport hall. Provide enough place for movement between.</p> <p>Activity description: All children are around in the sport hall or in the school yard. The teachers give instructions how to move.</p> <p>First instruction: run and stop. On run, they run forward or in other direction, on stop they stop at one place or stand on one leg.</p> <p>Second instruction: stand and sit. On stand, they should stand on the chair, on sit should sit on the chair or bench.</p> <p>Third instruction: On run they stop and stand on one leg; on stop they run in different directions, on stand, they stand on the chair, on sit they sit on the chair or bench.</p> <p>Forth instruction: On run they stop and stand on one leg; on stop they run in different directions, on chair or the bench.</p>		
	Materials	Reflection	Modification
	Bench or chairs	<p>After 15 – 20 minutes of playing the game, children get together and discuss their experience and feelings. Some of the reflective questions can be: Was it difficult to memorize everything? What frustrated you? How did you feel during the game?</p>	<p>The movements and level of difficulty can be changed based on children age and ability.</p> <p>Modification with elements of intercultural communication: The game can be practices with implementing different cultural elements, for example manners of greeting. At the beginning, teacher should present two different types of greetings (ex: bowing specific for Japan, Thailand, Nepal and hand on the heard specific for Malaysia) as first instruction. On second they switch greetings. On third implement two other manners: hand shaking as in Middle East countries and chick kissing as in West European countries. On four switch the greetings.</p>

2.2. INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION FOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

<p>QUICKLY THROUGH THE LOOP</p> <p>Duration 10 minutes</p>	Activity
	<p>The children line up in a circle and listen to the teacher's explanations. The children are divided into two groups. They form a circle and hold hands. A hoop is placed between two children. The children now have to bring the hoop to the next person as quickly as possible without letting go of their hands. How they do it is up to them.</p> <p>Cooperative action: Children must work together to get to their common goal.</p> <p>Goal: Children should get through the hoop as quickly as possible without letting go of their hands. Nonverbal communication: children are not allowed to talk during this task, the focus is only on movement and cooperation.</p> <p>First round: The children do a test round without encountering any difficulty. However, they are not allowed to speak in the first round either.</p> <p>2nd round: Competition between the two groups. Which group gets the hoop back to the beginning person faster? → nonverbal communication</p> <p>3rd round. Everyone closes their eyes and does a test round.</p> <p>4th round. Everyone closes their eyes and does a competition against the other group.</p> <p>If there is still time for a fifth round, you can unite the group and do a normal round.</p>
	Reflection
	<p>Reflective questions:</p> <p>Which round felt good/familiar?</p> <p>Which felt strange?</p> <p>Why?</p>

Game: Quickly through the loop

Game: Group twister atomic game

Game: Get together

<p>GROUP TWISTER ATOMIC GAME</p> <p>Duration 15 minutes</p>	<p>Activity</p> <p>All students walk through the gym.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - When the teacher stops the music, she calls a number into the room. - Then the students have to get together as quickly as possible to form this number. - Then the groups are given a task: the team is only allowed to stand with 5 legs on the floor, the team has to touch the floor with exactly 4 feet and 4 hands. - Now the pupils try to solve the task. When all groups have done it, the new round starts. - Variations: the groups play against each other. The team that takes the longest has to do 10 jumping jacks. The teacher shows the students an acrobatics card, which they have to imitate. <p>The students always form new groups and have to come up with new acrobatics in order to solve the task correctly.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - verbal communication: the students have to communicate with each other in order to form groups correctly and to agree on how they want to carry out the task.
	<p>Reflection</p> <p>Did you enjoy the game? How did you feel when you didn't have an idea what to do next? What did you do then?</p>
<p>GET TOGETHER</p> <p>Duration 15 minutes</p>	<p>Activity</p> <p>The members of a team get together in pairs for the exercise "Put yourselves together". One partner is now blindfolded. This partner must then fetch certain objects from the center of a circle. The objects are described to him by his sighted partner. After the practice phase, the game begins.</p> <p>The field is divided into two. 4 pairs are in the first half and the other 4 pairs are in the second half. In each half, the four pairs compete against each other at the same time. The pairs line up on their starting point and everyone has to get the same thing from the center together. The item is shown in the center so that everyone who sees recognizes the item. In the second round, the two-man teams switch roles. More rounds follow. The objects can multiply. The game becomes harder for the blind partner to listen to the sighted partner. In addition, the sighted partners must make sure that the "blind" do not collide. If 2 teams collide one must start again at the starting line</p> <p>Cooperative action: The children have to work together to get to their common goal.</p> <p>Verbal communication plays the main role: the partners have to talk to each other in order to find the object they are looking for as quickly as possible, since one of them is blindfolded and therefore cannot see anything. It's important to communicate so that nobody gets hurt and therefore you also have to listen carefully.</p>
	<p>Reflection</p>

	<p>Did you enjoy the game? What do you have to be able to do? Do you know similar games? Which ones? Where can you play the game?</p>
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<p>Many greetings</p> <p>Duration: 15 minutes</p>	<p>Activity</p>	
	<p>Gather students in a circle. Welcome students, ask for the group's different nationalities and introduce the lesson's topic. "All over the world people move and play together. Do you know any sports or games that are typical for certain countries?" How do you say hello? Circle formation and free movement through the hall. In the circle, different greetings typical greeting rituals are collected and are collected and presented. Ask students to walk around the hall. Whenever two participants meet, they greet each other with a with a different ritual. At the same time the participants can also talk about the forms of greeting they have developed new variations.</p>	
	<p>Reflection</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which form of greeting felt good/familiar? • Which felt strange? Why? • What ways of greeting each other do you use in your everyday life? 	<p>Tips for teachers</p> <p>Gather students in a circle and ask them to reflect on the experience. Possible guiding questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How did you feel during the different games?

<p>SIGHTS FROM ALL OVER THE WORLD</p> <p>Duration</p>	<p>Activity</p>	
	<p>One student is the game leader. The game leader names a way of moving in which all the other participants move through the hall. After a short time, the game leader calls out a number between 2 and 6 in any language. The other participants get together in small groups according to the number. The group now has the task of representing a place of interest or something characteristic of the country in whose language the command was given. Then the game leader changes.</p>	
	<p>Reflection</p> <p>Reflection questions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Did you enjoy the game? 	<p>Tips for teachers</p> <p>Which games were perhaps already familiar to you, which games have similarities with games you know?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are there any similarities with games you know?

15-20 minutes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How did you feel when you didn't understand the language immediately? • What did you do then? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do you personally take away from the experience? • How can you use the experience in your everyday life?
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GAMES FROM AROUND THE WORLD Duration 45 minutes	Activity
	In the image of a journey around the world, students get to know different games, which may also contain familiar elements.
	Example of games
	<p>Feather catching (game from Nigeria, Africa) The participants form pairs and stand behind each other. The person at the back of each team has a feather or a ribbon attached to the waistband of his/her trousers and holds on to the hip or shoulders of his/her partner. At the signal of the instructor, the teams try to get as many as possible from the other teams, always keeping the team together. team must always stay together.</p>
	<p>Loo K'bah Zee (game from Myanmar, Asia) The participants stand in a circle. One participant has a rice bag. The participants put their hands behind their backs so that a small rice bag or similar can be placed inside. One participant starts and walks around the outside of the circle. the rice bag into someone's hand. As soon as the rice bag is put down, the participant walks around the participant without the rice bag walks clockwise and the one with the rice bag walks counter-clockwise around the outside of the circle. Whichever of the two arrives last at the free place starts the game with the game with the rice bag from the beginning.</p>

Ball race (game from Oceania, Australia)

The participants form two teams and stand behind each other. The first participant of each team stands approx. 10 m in front of the center line. The first team member in front must now try to throw the ball over the center line. He/she then retrieves the ball, lines up at the back of his/her own team and the ball is passed to the front. If the ball does not cross the center line, the participant has a second try.

Pok ta Pok (game from Mexico, North/Central America)

Place a hoop in each of two opposite goals at shoulder height. at shoulder height. The participants form two teams.

	<p>In this old Mayan game, a ball (water polo or similar) may be played with all parts of the with all parts of the body except the feet and hands. The aim is to get the ball through the opponent's hoop. This leads to a point. If the ball falls on the ground, the other team gets the ball.</p>	
	<p>City-country-river-language In the middle of the hall there is a hoop in which the cards of the game quartets are laid out face up. Each card shows either a city, a country, a river or a language typical of the country. Four cards (city, country, river, language) make up a country quartet. The participants form four teams and stand at the same distance from each other and from the center of the hall. from each other and from the center of the hall. One team member runs to the hoop and picks up a card. The next participant then runs and looks for another matching card. The game ends when all the cards have been taken out of the hoop in the middle. Cards can also be exchanged with the other teams.</p>	
	<p>Lion King All participants sit or lie on their backs on the floor in the hall. floor. The sitting/lying participants make a petrified face. Two participants go around and try to make the other participants grin or laugh by funny poses to make the other participants grin or laugh. The other participants must not be touched. If one participant laughs, he/she can support the two participants and go with them.</p>	
	Reflection	Tips for teachers
	<p>Reflection questions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Did you enjoy the game? • What do you have to be able to do? Do you know similar games? • Which ones? Where can you play the game? 	<p>Which games were perhaps already familiar to you, which games have similarities with games you know?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are there any similarities with games you know? • What do you personally take away from the experience? • How can you use the experience in your everyday life?
Resources	<p>Barbarash, L.: Spiele rund um die Welt. Interkulturelle Ideen für Sportunterricht und Freizeit. Mülheim a.d.R.: Verlag an der Ruhr, 2009</p> <p>Hofmann, E.-M. und Rodloff, S.: Gespielt wird auf der ganzen Welt. Seelze: Kallmeyersche, 2002</p> <p>Sportjugend NRW im Landessportbund NRW e.V. (Hrsg.): Arbeitshilfe Spiele spielen. 4. überarbeitete Auflage. Duisburg, Eigenverlag, 2005</p>	

3.0. EXAMPLES OF ACTIVITIES FOR INTERCULTURAL SENSITIVITY

Intercultural sensitivity reflects the ability of individuals to understand and accept the existence of cultural differences, understand the way that cultural differences affect behaviors, attitudes and understanding of people. It means developing an ability to respect different cultures, to treat all cultures as equal and valid, and to demonstrate empathy, openness and flexibility in communication and everyday living with people from different cultures. In short, intercultural sensitivity means a person responding well to cultural differences and connecting with culturally different people. Intercultural sensitivity is higher level of intercultural awareness and intercultural communication as it means not only being aware of own culture and existence of different cultures and communicating well, but also desire to learn, respect and accept cultural differences; understand people from different background and accept them regardless the differences. Intercultural sensitivity can be achieved by developing certain attitudes such as self – control, self – respect, interest for other cultures, reconciliation, show respect, willingness to modify personal behavior etc.

Educational problem: Schools nowadays are more often attended by students with different background (cultural, ethnical, religiose etc). Such background reflects on students' behavior, attitudes and communication with classmates and other children and can often leads to misunderstanding, arguments, and conflicts. Therefore, through variety of curricular and extracurricular activities, schools should be focused on promoting cultural diversity, emphasizing values of being different, interacting with people from different cultures and building strong relationships with them.

Aim: The selected activities aims to develop students' cultural sensitivity by experiencing cultural diversity, build strong relationships with people from other cultures and enjoy cultural interaction through different movement games and cooperative tasks and activities.

Learning Outcomes

Students will be able to:

- communicate effectively with people from other cultures, show respect and appreciation for their cultural and tradition and support cultural diversity.
- to observe and identify differences related to culture and to learn to act in supportive and respectful manner.
- acknowledge other cultures by participating in different traditional games, dances and other culturally based activities and modify personal behavior in order to show respect and experience mutual dependance regardless of gender, race etc,
- build strong relationships with people from other cultures by experiencing their culture through participation in traditional and multicultural games and sports, collaborative games and other culturally based activities.
- experience empathy for other cultures and openness to diversity by participating in different traditional and multicultural games and sports, cooperative tasks and different cultural activities.

Implementation: Students will explore, practice and acquire different activities that are culturally based and different from their own culture, develop understanding for diversity and modify their behavior in order to show respect, interest and acknowledgment. Supportive behavior and recognition of other cultural groups will lead to strong relationships with people from other cultures based on respect and empathy. The students will have an active role in learning while the teacher's role will be mainly supportive. During the activities cooperative learning and student-centered teaching approach will be adopted. Strategies of collaboration, active learning and discovery will be applied, where students will have active participation, and each student will have the opportunity to learn different things and participate in different activities.

Facility of implementation: Schoolyard, court, classroom.

Resources: Bronikowska, M., & Laurent, JF. (2015). Recall: Games of the Past – Sports for Today. Frankfurt: TAFISA

3.1. INTERCULTURAL SENSITIVITY FOR PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

GAME “MY CULTURAL HAT” Duration 30 minutes	Activity Different types of hats specific to different cultures should be provided. Cards with pictures can be used as an option as well. Children can make them from paper or teachers can prepare them previously. At the beginning of the game, the teacher will instruct children which culture they belong to and to choose hat accordingly. At different parts of the sport hall, there should be a hoop or marked circle with picture that refers to culture (picture from the according hats for smaller children, flag, or country name for older ones). Activity Description: All children stand in a circle at a distance from the center of the circle where the teacher is. Once the teacher throws in air all hats or pictures with different hats, each child should search for the hat/picture from hat that responds to the culture that the child was appointed to. When he/she finds the appropriate hat/picture should move fast to find the hoop with same picture (culture). The teacher checks if everyone is in the right place and after that collects the cards and repeats the game again. The task requires following body signs and identification of the right direction, not to crash into other children, to do fast movements, to have a good coordination, space awareness etc.			
	Materials <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hats specific to different cultures or pictures with hats specific to different cultures Hoops cards with culture specific aspect or country name. The number of hats/cars will depend on the number of children in the class.	Reflection After 15 – 20 minutes of playing the game, children get together and discuss their experience and feelings.	Modification To make the game more interesting, the children can be appointed in different cultures after several repetitions or cultural elements can be changed.	Tips for teachers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Give students clear instructions and suggestions about the movements that they can use. Allow students to communicate, make decisions, and define their own strategy. Encourage fair play among teams.

	Activity Activity Organization: The teacher prepares cards according to the number of children in the class. One card for every child. On each card there is a flag and name of the country and on the back side, a picture of the manner of greeting specific for the culture in selected country (ex: hand waving and saying Cao Cao in Italy; bowing followed with arm movement specific for Japan and other Asian cultures, hand shaking in Middle and South Europe etc). It can be several cards with the same greeting type. On different places in the sport hall or school yard, hoops should be placed on the ground with a card from different country.
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GREETING GAME Duration 30 minutes	Activity Description: Before starting the game, each child picks a card and analyses the way of greeting that should perform. All children are placed in different places around the sport hall or school yard. On the sign of the teacher, they all start to move around in different manner determined by the teacher (running in different directions, hopping etc). At the sign of the teacher “Greet your friend”, each child should find a partner, stop in front of him/her and greet it according to its personal card. This should be repeated several times. After several repetitions, the teacher gives a sign “Find your country” and all children that represent the same country should find their hoop. The teacher checks if everyone is in the right place and after that collects the cards and repeats the game again. The task requires fast reaction and change of direction and speed of movement, attention not to crash into other children, to react fast on teachers’ signs, to have a good coordination, space awareness etc.			
	Materials	Reflection	Modification	Tips for teachers
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • activity cards • hoops 	After 15 – 20 minutes of playing the game, children get together and discuss their experience and feelings. Some of the reflective questions can be: How did you feel during the game? How did you feel representing another country that is not your native country? Was it difficult to perform different types of greeting? Did you learn something new?	To make the game more interesting, the children can choose different cultures after several repetitions or movement tasks can be changed (ex: running backward, jump on one leg, walk in kneeling position etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Give students clear instructions and suggestions about the movements that they can use. • Allow students to communicate, make decisions, and define their own strategy. • Encourage fair play among teams.
Traditional clothes Duration: 30 minutes.	Activity			
	<p>Activity Organization: Before the activity, the teacher finds different parts from traditional clothes from different countries (children can also bring some clothes from home). It should be 4 – 5 pieces for clothes for each country (group). The number of groups should be defined based on the number of children in the class (optimal is 3 groups). In front of each group, there are cones markers and elastic tap, horizontally over the floor, distance from it for about 30sm. Each group is named by some country that traditional clothes should be done. On the opposite side of column, a basket with different parts from traditional clothing all added (ex: mariachi head, kimono, sari, scarf, short shirt as kilt etc).</p> <p>Activity Description: Children are divided into groups (2 – 4 groups), depending on the number of children in the class. They stay in columns. On teachers sign, the second children from each group runs forward passing the obstacles, takes one piece of clothes that represent his/her country traditional clothes, pass the obstacles again and at the end, dresses up the child that stands as first in the column. The game is over when all elements of the traditional clothes for one country are dressed up as the first child in the column. The teacher checks if everyone is in the right place. The task requires speed, coordination, and cooperation.</p>			
	Materials	Reflection	Modification	Tips for teachers

	different pieces of wardrobe specific to some country traditional (national costume), basket for clothes, cones markers, other sport equipment as obstacle.	After 15 – 20 minutes of playing the game, children get together and discuss their experience and feelings.	different movement tasks, with different levels of difficulty can be given. Movement should be selected based on students' age and possibilities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Give students clear instructions and suggestions about the movements that they can use. • Allow students to communicate, make decisions, and define their own strategy. • Encourage fair play among teams.
TRADITIONAL GAME: BLINDMAN'S BUFF (COLIN MAILLARD) (Bronikowska & Laurent, 2018)	Activity			
	<p>Activity Organization: Select an area of play suitable to the number of players (appropriate size). One player is chosen randomly to be the chaser and is blindfolded with a scarf.</p> <p>Background of the game: "Colin Maillard" is an ancient game that traces back to Greece 2000 years ago. It has spread all over the world and is popular with adults as well as children. The origin of the name of its French version is obscure. Michel Tournier, in his book "Le Vent Paraclet" (1979), suggests that Colin was a figure from the Nordic mythology, a warrior coming from Flanders that used to fight with a mallet ("Maillet") and, because of an injury that turned him blind, had to be guided by a valet to help him continue the fight in the battlefield. It could also be that Colin was a man that fought with a mallet and got blind during a Medieval battle against the French Lord of Leuven. Variations of "Colin Maillard" are called "Blindman's buff" in Great Britain, "Blindekuh" in Germany, "Blindbock" in Spain, "Kola onye tara gi okpo" in Nigeria, etc</p> <p>Activity Description: "Colin Maillard" turns around three times while the other players spread out in the area of play. Once "Colin Maillard" stands still, the other players start to provoke her/him either by moving, shouting, singing, or even tagging her/him (without pushing) to start a chase. They must, however, avoid being caught at the same time. Colin Maillard must manage to catch a player and guess the identity of that player. The face of the player can be touched to help with recognition. If the identity is correctly guessed, the player who is revealed becomes the new "Colin Maillard" and the game starts again. If not, the player that was caught is released and Colin Maillard must start a new chase. When the blindfolded Colin Maillard approaches an obstacle or moves too far out of the area of play, other players must provide a warning by shouting "Dare-devil!" Through these game children improve endurance, balance, and speed. The game requires cooperation and communication skills and memory.</p> <p>Number of players: 3 – 15 children at the age of 5+</p> <p>Country of origin: <i>France</i></p>			
	Duration 30 minutes.	Materials	Reflection	Tips for teachers

	A scarf	After 15 – 20 minutes of playing the game, children get together and discuss their experience and feelings.	<p>Tips for teachers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Give students clear instructions and suggestions about the movements that they can use. • Allow students to communicate, make decisions, and define their own strategy. • Encourage fair play among teams.
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3.2. INTERCULTURAL SENSITIVITY FOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

<p>TRADITIONAL SPORTS</p> <p>Duration: 30 minutes</p>	Activity		
	<p>Activity Organization. The teacher in communication with students analyses which sports are traditional and specific for different countries. If some of the students in the class knows some of those sports, then is invited by the teacher to present it. If no, the teacher assign groups and delegates different tasks – each group to investigate a sport for country, learn basic movements, learn about the philosophy of the selected sport, learn basic elements etc.</p> <p>Following are some of the examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Japan – judo, aikido, sumo, karate • Ireland – Gaelic games • China – tai chi • Brazil – capoeira • Turkey – wrestling • India – yoga • New Zealand, Australia – rugby <p>Activity Description: When activity and presenter are selected, first a short presentation of the sport is organized – origins, rules, the sport nowadays. After that the presenter demonstrates the basic of the sports and all other either try some elements or play together (depending on selected sport). The selected students for the sport demonstrate the sport elements and later help others to master them. A help from the teacher or coach from local club are also welcomed.</p>		
	Materials	Reflection	Tips for teachers
<p>Videos from traditional sports from different countries</p> <p>Resources: http://hopsports.com/</p>	<p>After 30 minutes of playing the game, or practicing the sport, students get together and discuss their experience and feelings.</p> <p>Some of the reflective questions can be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How did you feel during trying new sport and new movements? • How did you feel representing another country that is not your native country? • Was it difficult to perform different elements? • Did you learn something new? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Give students clear instructions and task. • If you allocate teamwork, give students possibility to choose who they want to work with • Allow students to communicate, make decisions, give ideas for their presentation. 	

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are you motivated to learn more about the presented sport or the culture of that country in general? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourage students to investigate more for the sport and culture of the country of origin.
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<p>“FIND YOUR CULTURE, FIND YOUR HOME”</p> <p>Duration 30 minutes.</p>	Activity			
	<p>Activity Organization: The preparation can be made by the teacher or the teacher can delegate tasks to students. If tasks are delegated to students, they should be divided into different groups. The teacher or each group should investigate cultural specifics for different countries (food, music, traditional sports, dances, forms of greetings, greeting words etc). Based on that, prepare cards with pictures with 3 – 5 culturally specific elements for each country (each element on a separate card). Before starting the activity, all cards are mixed and put in one or several boxes (depending on the number of students). On different parts of the sport hall a flag from a selected country or a paper with the country's name is written.</p> <p>Activity Description: All students stand in a line at the end of the sports hall. The teacher instructs to move in different manners – running forward, running backward, hopping, jumping with two legs etc. On teacher's sign “find your home/ find your culture” students pick a card and run as fast as they can to the place marked for their country/ culture. The group that is completed first wins 5 points, next one 3, last one 1 (etc). In case of more groups, different point systems can be added. It can be repeated several times with different movement instructions and mixing groups. The task requires following teacher instructions attention not to crash into other students, to do fast movements, to have a good coordination, space awareness etc.</p>			
	Materials	Reflection	Modification	Tips for teachers
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • cards with specific cultural elements, • different equipment for relay games and obstacle track. 	<p>After 15 – 20 minutes of playing the game, students get together and discuss their experiences and feelings</p>	<p>The cards from different groups can be used for further activities and relay games. All students belonging to one “” culture/country” will be in the same team and do different obstacle paths. Also, different cultural elements can be used – for example on the teacher call “food” all students from different cultures with a “food card” should pass the relay track.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Give children clear instructions and tasks. • Allow students to communicate, make decisions, and define their own strategy. • Encourage fair play among teams.

Examples of cards for one team for the game “Find your culture, find your home”

Country:ITALY

Food

Transport

Traditions

Greetings

